

ZARAGOZA

CLIMATE-NEUTRAL BY 2030

The City of Zaragoza, in Spain, is situated in the Autonomous Community of Aragón and it is characterized by cold semi-arid climates (BSk).

With 973,8 km², Zaragoza has a population of 694,109 (2022), with expected growth for the next decades.

LEADING ECONOMIC SECTORS IN ZARAGOZA:

INDUSTRY

MANUFACTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS

TOURISM

KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY

MAIN SOURCES OF CO₂ EMISSIONS (2022):

INDUSTRY

DOMESTIC SERVICES

TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS

URBAN WASTE MANAGEMENT

AGRICULTURE

MAIN SOURCES OF ENERGY GENERATED :

RENEWABLES

OIL

NATURAL GAS

MOBILITY PATTERNS:

HALF OF THE POPULATION CHOSSES TO WALK, 27.5% USES PRIVATE VEHICLES, AND 23% COMMUTES ON PUBLIC TRANSPORT

SNAPSHOT OF ZARAGOZA ON CAPACITY BUILDING:

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

Governance and Policy
Implementation and technology

KEY AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

Financing and Business Models
Social Innovation

TOPICS OF INTEREST:

Innovative citizen and stakeholder engagement methods
Business Models for energy-related projects

Funded by the European Union

GOVERNANCE AND POLICY

In alignment with the EU climate neutrality goals for 2050, Spain adopted the Climate Change and Energy Transition Law in 2021, with specific goals for the decarbonisation of energy sector and sectoral targets for the built environment, transport system, and inclusion of renewable energies.

Based on the climate goals and plan established by the Central Government, climate policies and competencies are shared across the central, the Autonomous Communities, and local authorities.

The city of Zaragoza is part of the 100 EU Mission Cities. In 2023 Zaragoza received the EU Mission Label for their commitment to reach Climate Neutrality by 2030.

Within the city of Zaragoza, climate roles and responsibilities are shared across seven departments: Citizen Participation and internal regime; Economy, Digital Transformation and Transparency; Environment and Mobility; Social Policies; Culture, Education and Tourism; Urbanism, Infrastructures, Energy and Housing; and Finance and European Funds. All these departments are directly involved in the implementation of the city climate agenda.

The governance structure on climate city contract is led by the Directorate General for European Funds which liaises cross-cutting climate neutrality initiatives, facilitating the coordination among departments and following up with the Climate City Contracts process.

The municipality actively involves local entities and stakeholders in inter-sectoral consultations on climate initiatives, providing a forum for exchange, and climate awareness but also active co-creation in the Climate City Contracts process.

NATIONAL LEVEL:

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ENERGY TRANSITION LAW (2021)

IN ZARAGOZA:

INTER-DEPARTMENTAL COORDINATION ON CLIMATE

CROSS SECTORAL CLIMATE ACTION

CO-CREATION THROUGH CLIMATE CITY CONTRACTS

SOCIAL INNOVATION

Zaragoza recognizes a key role in mobilizing its local ecosystem of stakeholders and citizens to ensure an inclusive transition. First with workshops and awareness campaigns, and more recently through cross-sectoral Climate Commitments and Climate Empowerment initiative, the city strives to foster a collaborative ecosystem for the co-creation of climate solutions.

Despite the high priority placed on citizen and stakeholder engagement, levels of participation are generally low.

The main barriers to engagement are mostly due to a lack of awareness of climate change consequences, reluctance from communities to change behaviors, resisting interests from the industries involved in the transition, and lack of structured dialogue between the community and decision-makers.

Addressing energy poverty as well as supporting local businesses in the climate transition are key priorities.

In the pursuit of a just transition, Zaragoza incorporates specific measures to ensure social justice and gender equality in its participatory processes.

To improve its social engagement capacity, the city of Zaragoza is looking to innovate in the following areas:

INNOVATIVE COMMUNICATION CHANNELS (SUCH AS ICT)

ENGAGEMENT METHODS

IMPLEMENTATION AND TECHNOLOGY

The city of Zaragoza focuses on decarbonizing its Built Environment, Transport system, Industrial Processes and Product Use (IPPU).

When trying to reduce carbon emissions, Zaragoza faces challenges related to the fragmentation of responsibilities within the local government's organizational structure and the need for more targeted regulations and enabling policies. Bureaucratic hurdles and uncertain regulation on taxation and financing aspects are main barriers too.

Cross-sectoral commitment and citizen awareness are key social factors identified to overcome the implementation barriers. The municipality strives for more coordinated commitment among all sectors and targeted dialogue with the community of homeowners and tenants.

To enable emission reduction, the city focuses on Smart city projects, Sustainable and intelligent mobility, Renewable energy and efficiency, Water and nature-based solutions, and Circular economy.

As Lighthouse City in the project, Zaragoza has experience in designing and implementing Positive and Clean Energy Districts (PCEDs). The building and construction industry, SMEs, homeowners, and tenants are identified as essential stakeholders for a successful PCED implementation.

CLIMATE AND ENERGY DATA COLLECTION ANALYSIS

ADAPTATION SECTORS

LOCAL ENERGY RENEWABLE PRODUCTION

COLLABORATION

NEUTRALPATH key target sectors for the PCEDs implementation are: Built Environment, Energy and Mobility

FINANCING AND BUSINESS MODELS FOR PCEDS AND CLIMATE NEUTRALITY

The city of Zaragoza uses the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy (Regulation (EU) 2020/852 as Investment Readiness Assessment tool and the city has experience in energy efficiency investments, leveraging public funding, third-party financing, and innovative financing schemes on Citizen Finance like Crowdfunding.

Based on the financing gaps identified, Zaragoza is seeking to enhance its financing skills on how to improve the aggregation of investments for climate and environmental projects, creating investment risk mitigation options, and develop effective business models for energy-related projects.

As part of its Climate City Contract, Zaragoza has developed an Investment Plan as a comprehensive long-term economic and financial strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2030.

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

- Third-party financing
- Citizen Finance
- Blended Finance

INTERESTED IN LEARNING ABOUT:

Business models for energy-related projects

The Capacity Building Program will support the upskilling of public authorities and local communities across these key cross-cutting areas and the Key Target Sectors to enable successful PCED implementation and unlock the systemic transformation necessary to achieve climate neutrality.

If you want to know more:

Climate City Contract

Zaragoza EU Mission Label

Participatory Budgets

neutralpath.eu/

Funded by
the European Union